

Roll-to-roll mechanical exfoliation for large-area van der Waals films with preserved crystallographic alignment

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ABSTRACT

Anisotropic two-dimensional (2D) materials such as black phosphorus (BP), GeS or CrSBr, exhibit direction-dependent optical and electronic properties that are highly desirable for polarization-sensitive detection, waveguiding, and directionally tuned transport. However, scalable fabrication of large-area films with preserved in-plane crystallographic alignment remains a key challenge. Here, we present a roll-to-roll-inspired mechanical exfoliation technique as a general, low-cost, and scalable strategy to produce large-area films of in-plane anisotropic van der Waals nanosheets. Polarized transmittance measurements confirm the presence of predominant optical anisotropy across centimeter-scale areas, and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) reveals that individual nanosheets exhibit consistent in-plane orientation at the nanoscale. Furthermore, we fabricate anisotropic electronic devices and demonstrate that the films inherit the direction-dependent conductivity of their constituent flakes. This method offers a broadly applicable route for integrating anisotropic nanosheets of 2D materials into scalable optoelectronic and sensing technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Since the isolation of graphene and other 2D materials using mechanical exfoliation with Scotch tape,^[1] the development of new production methods has become an essential task to transition these materials from laboratory research to real-world applications. Early on, it became clear that no single production method would be universally optimal; instead, a diverse set of techniques is required, each best suited for specific applications. For instance, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) enables the fabrication of large-area films with precise thickness control and excellent electronic properties^[2,3], making CVD ideal for the production of high-performance electronic devices. However, its high cost makes it unsuitable for cost-sensitive applications such as structural nanocomposites, where liquid-phase exfoliation offers a more economical route to large-scale material production.^[4-7] For low-cost electronics, liquid-phase exfoliation combined with inkjet printing or other similar approaches has been proposed,^[8-12] though significant challenges remain open. The properties of such printed devices are largely determined by flake-to-flake junctions rather than the intrinsic properties of the individual flakes^[13]. Similarly, electrochemical exfoliation,^[14,15] which produces flakes with high aspect ratios, combined with deposition techniques like Langmuir-Blodgett assembly^[16-18], can lead to more homogeneous distributions but faces limitations with uses of surfactant or stabilizing agent and limited scalability for large-area production.

In parallel, and since the successful exfoliation of materials like black phosphorus (BP), ReS₂, and TiS₃, interest in van der Waals materials with intrinsic in-plane anisotropy has grown^[19-23]. These materials provide opportunities to explore fundamental quasi-1D physics and applications such as polarization optics.^[24-29] However, high-yield production techniques for large-area fabrication of these materials, while preserving uniform crystal orientation, are limited to only a few methods. While CVD can achieve

oriented growth through controlled nucleation on templated substrates,^[30,31] its reliance on high temperatures, vacuum equipment, and slow growth rates makes it impractical for applications requiring scalable and low-cost production methods such as structural nanocomposites, flexible sensors, or disposable electronics. In contrast, liquid phase exfoliation provides a most promising low-cost route to film fabrication. However, the randomly oriented resulting flakes lack any preferred crystallographic alignment across the film.

In order to address these challenges, here we have used a roll-to-roll mechanical exfoliation method capable of producing densely packed films of exfoliated flakes over large areas. While roll-to-roll techniques have previously been used to generate large-area coatings of layered materials^[32], those earlier approaches typically yielded films with randomly oriented flakes and no control over in-plane crystallographic alignment. In the present work, we introduce a key modification: we carefully select a single-crystalline flake with well-defined anisotropic shape and mount it on the source roll with a controlled in-plane orientation. Combined with the directional nature of the exfoliation process (which involves no twisting or uncontrolled shear) this ensures that exfoliated flakes inherit the crystallographic orientation of the parent crystal. As a result, we obtain macroscopic films in which the flakes are not only densely packed and uniformly distributed, but also preferentially crystallographically aligned. This enhanced control over flake orientation enables the scalable fabrication of anisotropic films ideally suited for direction-sensitive electronic and optoelectronic applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We start by illustrating the exfoliation steps and transfer process, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1a (top) shows a bulk flake of BP cleaved onto the surface of Nitto SPV 224 tape (source tape hereafter). Although other adhesive tapes such as thermal release films can also be used, we selected Nitto SPV 224 due to its widespread use in exfoliation protocols, wide availability, and compatibility with room-temperature or mild thermal transfer. To ensure crystallographic alignment of the exfoliated flakes, we select a single macroscopic BP crystal with a well-defined anisotropic shape and mount it individually on the source roll. This guarantees that all exfoliated flakes share a preferential crystallographic orientation. Notably, the absolute orientation of the crystal with respect to the rolling direction does not need to be predetermined, as long as it is consistently maintained during the process. A control experiment highlighting the importance of this placement strategy is provided in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information. The exfoliation process is performed by rolling the two cylinders against each other using an electric motor. After this procedure, the material is distributed across both tapes. The source tape, as shown in Figure 1a (bottom), contains larger and bulkier flakes. Therefore, the acceptor tape, on the top cylinder, is used for further processing. This acceptor tape (see Figure 1b) is removed from the top cylinder for subsequent transfer. To transfer the film onto a target substrate, the tape is cut to the desired size and gently pressed onto the surface. A cotton swab is used to minimize air gaps and ensure uniform contact between tape and substrate. The surface is then heated to 100 °C for 5 minutes which leads to an effective thermal release of the film. Finally, the tape is peeled off, resulting in the transfer of nearly all flakes onto the target surface (Figure 1c). In this work, we primarily use polycarbonate (PC), silicon substrates with a silicon oxide capping layer (SiO_2/Si) and Si_3N_4 holey membrane transmission electron microscopy (TEM) grids as target substrates. To validate the homogeneity and morphology of the exfoliated films, we performed atomic force

microscopy measurements and optical microscopy-based surface coverage analysis (Supplementary Figures S2 and S3). For BP films, the flakes show a typical thickness range of 20-60 nm, and surface coverage exceeds 90% in most regions.

Figure 1. Roll-to-roll exfoliation of black phosphorus (BP) crystals. (a) Image of the assembled high throughput mechanical exfoliation setup, showing a macroscopic BP crystal before (top) and after exfoliation (bottom). (Inset) Zoomed in picture of the BP crystal before placing it onto the tape where one can readily observe a marked anisotropy. (b) Optical image of the exfoliated BP crystals on adhesive tape forming a continuous film of interconnected flakes. (c) Photographs illustrating the transfer process of the exfoliated BP film from the adhesive tape onto a SiO₂ substrate. The tape is adhered onto the surface to the substrate, heated up to 100 °C for 5 minutes prior to the peeling off.

Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and four-dimensional STEM (4D-STEM) techniques were used to assess the crystal orientation of roll-to-roll mechanically exfoliated black phosphorus flakes, transferred onto holey Si_3N_4 membranes. Figure 2a presents an annular dark field (ADF) image of a region approximately $6 \times 6 \mu\text{m}^2$ in size. A high amount of flakes, with homogeneous size ranges in the few microns range, is observed.

Crystal orientation mapping was carried out using 4D-STEM in nano-beam configuration. Under these conditions, the electron beam is slightly converged to form a nanometer-scale probe, producing nano-beam electron diffraction (NBED) patterns, as shown in Figure 2b. As the beam is scanned across the sample, diffraction patterns are registered at each probe position, allowing to obtain crystallographic information with nanometric spatial resolution^[33]. Local crystal orientation is extracted from these diffraction patterns by measuring the angle (θ) between the horizontal axis and the reciprocal lattice vector (\vec{g}) corresponding to the short lattice vector of the crystal, as indicated in Figure 2b. By tracking this angle as a function of probe position, we obtain a crystal orientation map with nanometric spatial resolution. An orientation map obtained this way is depicted in Figure 2c in a false colour scale. The homogeneity observed highlights that the crystal orientation is well preserved within each flake, supporting the finding that they are single crystal in nature. Small variations are encountered between different flakes, marked by subtle colour shade differences. This trend is better represented in the histogram (inset of Figure 2 c), The average orientation is $\langle\theta\rangle = 36.3^\circ \pm 4.1^\circ$, with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of $\sim 15^\circ$, indicating a narrow angular dispersion. This confirms that the crystallographic alignment is well preserved across both nano- and micro-metric length scales, i.e., within individual flakes and across

neighboring flakes. Pixels corresponding to regions of overlapped flakes exhibit undefined orientation and appear as outliers in the dataset.

In order to get further evidence of the intra-flake structure, high resolution STEM images were collected. Figure 2d presents a representative atomic resolution ADF image of one of the flakes, tilted down the exfoliation direction $[020]$, with a sketch of the structure overlaid. No major defects are observed, confirming the good crystalline quality of the flakes and in good agreement with the laterally averaged orientation determined by NBED maps. Supporting Information Figure S4 shows further atomic resolution STEM-HAADF images and TEM selected area diffraction patterns of several exfoliated flakes over a larger lateral distance, depicting the crystalline quality of the exfoliated flakes.

Figure 2. Scanning transmission electron microscopy study of roll-to-roll mechanically exfoliated black phosphorus flakes. (a) ADF image of the explored region, showing a collection of neighboring flakes transferred onto a Si₃N₄ TEM membrane grid. (b) NBED pattern of a black phosphorus flake. The crystal orientation is determined by measuring the angle (θ) between the horizontal axis and the reciprocal vector corresponding to the short lattice vector of the crystal (\vec{g}). (c) Crystal orientation map, obtained from the NBED experiment. Each pixel is colored according to the corresponding measured θ value. The inset displays the histogram of angle values present in the image. (d) Atomic resolution ADF image of a flake tilted down the exfoliation direction [020], overlaid with a structural model of black phosphorus.

While 4D-STEM provides direct evidence of crystallographic alignment at the nanoscale, its low throughput limits its use for large-area assessment. Therefore, selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) on individual flakes was also employed to determine their in-plane orientation over longer lateral length scales in combination with optical linear dichroism - the dependence of optical absorption on the polarization direction of incident light. To characterize the linear dichroism of the flakes, we employed a Motic BA 310 MET optical microscope operated in transmission mode. A motorized rotator holding a linear polarizer was positioned between the microscope lamp and the condenser lenses. Images were acquired at various rotation angles, with 0° defined as the polarizer axis aligned parallel to the horizontal axis of the microscope's imaging window (see Supporting Information Figure S5). For a subset of these flakes, atomic-resolution STEM images were also acquired to confirm the orientation and crystalline quality inferred from the diffraction patterns. Linear dichroism measurements were obtained on the same flakes, finding strong agreement between the direction of maximum transmittance and the crystallographic axes identified by SAED.^[19] Figures S6 and S7 in the Supporting Information present representative results for two sets of BP flakes oriented at $\sim 30^\circ$ and $\sim 0^\circ$ (zigzag direction), demonstrating the close correspondence between the optical and electron diffraction data. We can conclude that linear dichroism provides a faster and more practical alternative to evaluate whether the flakes in a film are consistently oriented.

Having established this idea, Figure 3a and Figure 3b show examples of microscopy images of a BP film onto a PC substrate acquired under two different illumination conditions (the orientation of the linear polarizer is indicated in the insets of the figures). Under the polarization condition shown in (a), most flakes display lower transmittance compared to the condition in (b). These two orientations correspond to the angles yielding

minimum and maximum transmittance during a full 360° rotation of the linear polarizer. Interestingly, this straightforward measurement provides reliable and powerful information about the crystal orientation in the flakes: BP absorption is significantly higher when the incident light is linearly polarized along the x-axis (commonly referred to as the armchair direction) compared to the y-axis (also known as the zigzag direction).^[19] Figure 3c exhibits polar plots of the green-channel transmittance (normalized to the maximum value to facilitate comparison between flakes of different thicknesses), as a function of the angle between the linear polarizer axis and the horizontal axis, for randomly selected flakes across the previously captured images (highlighted with crosses). All plots show a remarkable alignment of the BP flakes. Figure 3c also includes a polar histogram with the angle of maximum transmittance of the studied flakes, indicating the film most probable zig-zag direction. The histogram is very narrow, indeed indicating a good alignment of all the flakes forming the film. This method proves to be an efficient way to characterize the crystal orientation of the films studied in this work.

While BP is used throughout the main text as a representative example, the roll-to-roll exfoliation protocol is equally applicable to other anisotropic van der Waals materials, provided they meet key criteria. Specifically, this alignment-preserving exfoliation technique requires materials that (i) are mechanically exfoliable, with strong in-plane bonding and weak interlayer van der Waals forces, and (ii) are available as high-quality, macroscopic single crystals. These conditions ensure that the initial bulk crystal can be mounted with a well-defined crystallographic orientation, which as discussed earlier is critical to maintain the global alignment of the exfoliated flakes across the substrate.

As shown in Supporting Information Figure S8, we demonstrate the successful fabrication of aligned films for additional layered anisotropic materials, including CrSBr, MoO₃, GeS, and As₂S₃. These results confirm the broader applicability of the method to a variety

of anisotropic van der Waals crystals. In contrast, materials that are only available in powder form, or those lacking marked cleavage anisotropy (e.g., due to limited contrast between interlayer and intralayer bonding), are less compatible with this approach.

To further support the generality of the method, we performed a statistical flake-size analysis for three additional anisotropic van der Waals materials: CrSBr, GeS, and MoO₃. As shown in Supporting Information Figure S9, all three materials yield elongated flakes with high aspect ratios (length-to-width), consistent with effective cleavage along their crystallographic axes.

Figure 3. Optical characterization of BP anisotropic films. Transmission mode optical microscopy images of BP films on a polycarbonate (PC) substrate, displaying variations in transmittance intensity when two different linear polarization light configurations are used (inset arrows indicate the direction of the linearly polarized transmitted light). (c) Polar plot of transmittance intensity versus linearly polarized light angle for 50 individual black phosphorus (BP) flakes, showcasing the anisotropic optical properties along the armchair (minimum of transmittance) and zigzag (maximum of transmittance) crystallographic directions. Overlaid is a polar histogram indicating the distribution of maximum transmittance directions for all flakes, demonstrating a consistent alignment of the flakes with a predominant orientation.

To thoroughly characterize the anisotropic properties of the fabricated films, it is essential to analyse multiple areas across the entire film to ensure that the anisotropic behaviour remains consistent and uniform. Figure 4a presents an image of the centimetre scale film

obtained right after the exfoliation process. The colored squares indicate the areas where linear dichroism measurements were conducted to identify the crystal orientation of 25 individual BP flakes in each highlighted area. To enhance the visualization, we represent the zigzag direction (with respect to the horizontal axis of the imaging window of the microscope) of each analysed flake as a dot marker in Figure 4b. See Supporting Information Figure S10 for the polar plots and the polar histogram corresponding to Figure 4b. The distribution of these dots demonstrates that flakes from different areas consistently share the same zigzag orientation. This indicates that the optical anisotropic properties of BP are preserved across the film, even when the areas are separated by significant distances. A slight overall shift can be observed in the dataset, which we attribute to a minor misalignment between the tape and the horizontal axis of the microscope, an effect that becomes noticeable due to the extended length of the tape.

While the overall orientation coherence is high, a small angular dispersion is present in some areas (e.g., a full width at half maximum of $\sim 20^\circ$ in the worst case), which we attribute to minor stochastic misalignments during the exfoliation process. These likely originate from local drift or partial rotation of weakly adhered flakes at the tape interface, particularly for thinner or loosely bound crystallites. Nonetheless, this residual dispersion is significantly lower than that observed in conventional exfoliation methods and does not compromise the macroscopic alignment of the film.

Additionally, it is important to evaluate the precision of the transfer process to ensure its suitability for fabricating devices or other structures that can harness the anisotropic properties of the material. This is very important for the assembly of van der Waals heterostructures made out of anisotropic van der Waals materials forming films with a well-defined preferential angle between their crystalline directions.

Figure 4. Long-range analysis of BP anisotropic films. (a) Photograph of a large-area BP film spanning several centimeters, with colored squares indicating regions where optical characterization measurements, like those shown in Figure 2, were performed to evaluate the alignment of the BP flakes forming the film. (b) Plot showing flake orientation consistency across different regions of the film. Each group of colored dots represents measurements from a specific zone, with the uniformity of angles indicating the preserved alignment and anisotropy of flakes over long distances.

Figure 5a illustrates the transfer of five BP films forming a fan-like configuration, where each stripe-shaped film is rotated approximately 22° relative to the previous one. Within each stripe, we measured the orientation of the zigzag direction of individual flakes using polarized transmittance, and then plotted these values as individual points in Figure 5b. The results demonstrate a strong linear correlation between the macroscopic transfer angle of the tape and the crystallographic orientation of the flakes, indicating that the flake alignment can be reliably controlled through the macroscopic transfer geometry.

To further test how resilient the achieved anisotropy is under mechanical deformation, we transferred the exfoliated films onto flexible polycarbonate substrates and evaluated their linear dichroism response before and after repeated bending. Specifically, the sample was subjected to 20 bending cycles with a radius of curvature of ~ 1.4 cm (see Supporting Information Figure S11). The dichroic signal remained unchanged, indicating

that both the flake alignment and adhesion to the substrate are preserved under moderate mechanical stress, highlighting the suitability of the films for flexible electronics applications.

Figure 5. Correlation between transfer angle and flake orientation in BP films. (a) Fan-like arrangement of BP films transferred at angles ranging from 0° to 90° in ~22° increments. Colored squares denote regions where flake alignment measurements, like those shown in Figure 3 and 4, were taken. (b) Plot illustrating the relationship between transfer angle and the armchair orientation of flakes, based on maximum transmittance intensity. The dashed line has slope = 1, confirming precise control of flake orientation via the macroscopic transfer angle of the tape.

To assess whether the anisotropic properties of individual flakes are preserved at the device level, we investigate the electrical transport in networks of interconnected flakes and examine whether the collective film retains directional dependence in its conductivity. Using photolithography, we designed an array of electrodes converging toward a central point, with a gap of 60 microns between opposing electrodes (see Supporting Information Figure S12 and related discussion for further details). Each adjacent electrode pair is separated by an angle of 45 degrees, as shown in Figure 6a (top). After performing the roll-to-roll exfoliation of the BP film, its zigzag orientation was

determined through linear dichroism measurement (Figure 6b), and the film was transferred then onto the electrode array to establish connections between the contacts (Figure 6a, bottom).

Electrical transport was then measured across different angles by selecting various pairs of opposing electrodes and applying a 1 V bias between source and drain. The measured current values were plotted on a polar graph (Figure 6c) and fitted using a quadratic cosine function, capturing the periodic angular dependence characteristic of anisotropic conductivity. The resulting pattern reveals a maximum conductivity along the armchair direction of the BP film and a minimum along the zigzag direction. This behavior is consistent with previous studies on single BP flakes, which report enhanced charge transport along the armchair axis due to its intrinsically higher carrier mobility compared to the zigzag direction^[19].

The resulting anisotropy ratio, defined as $\sigma_{\text{armchair}}/\sigma_{\text{zigzag}}$, falls in the range of ~ 1.1 – 2 across multiple devices. These values are in good agreement with those reported for mechanically exfoliated single-flake BP devices, where anisotropy ratios of ~ 1.7 have been observed,^[19] supporting the preferential preservation of both crystallographic orientation and transport anisotropy in our large-area films.

This agreement is particularly noteworthy given that our films are composed of partially overlapping nanosheets and necessarily include flake-to-flake junctions. Despite this granular microstructure, the observed angular dependence of the conductivity confirms that the in-plane anisotropy is effectively inherited from the original bulk crystal. The directional transport remains aligned with the crystallographic axes, indicating that the preferential flake orientation governs the device-scale behavior rather than being dominated by random inter-flake resistance. Additional transport measurements on five

other devices are provided in Supporting Information Figure S13, and the corresponding raw IV curves are shown in Figures S14 and S15.

Figure 6. Anisotropic conductivity analysis of BP films. (a, top left) Device featuring eight gold electrodes arranged in a circular pattern on a SiO₂ substrate, separated by 45° and converging toward a central 60 μm diameter circle without contact. (a, bottom right) Image of the bottom half of the device after transferring a BP film, connecting the electrodes. (b) Polar plot of transmittance intensity, identifying the zigzag orientation of the BP film, carried out on the tape before transfer. (d) Polar plot of current measured at 1 V for different pairs of drain-source electrodes forming different angles. The peanut-shaped pattern in the current plot corresponds well to the anisotropic transmittance, confirming higher conductivity along the armchair direction.

To further demonstrate the applicability of our alignment-preserving exfoliation method for device fabrication, we validated the electrical and optoelectronic anisotropy of CrSBr films. Electrical transport measurements in devices with radial electrode geometries revealed a clear angular dependence of conductivity, with maximum current flow along the crystallographic *a*-axis direction, as determined from direct optical inspection of the ribbon-like flakes (see Supporting Information Figure S16). In addition, we fabricated a

polarization-sensitive photodetector based on a CrSBr film transferred onto a flexible polycarbonate substrate, with electrodes patterned at 45° with respect to the a -axis to isolate the intrinsic anisotropic response from the artifacts that may arise from the interaction of incoming light with the metal electrodes edges. The resulting photocurrent exhibited a sinusoidal polarization dependence aligned with the crystal orientation, confirming the preservation of optoelectronic anisotropy at the device level (Supporting Information Figure S17). These results demonstrate the potential of our approach for the scalable integration of anisotropic van der Waals materials into functional devices.

CONCLUSION

We report a low-cost, roll-to-roll-inspired mechanical exfoliation technique for producing large-area networks of anisotropic nanosheets with preferential crystallographic alignment. Using black phosphorus as a model system we demonstrate that the resulting films consist of extended networks of interconnected flakes that share a preferential in-plane orientation. The approach was successfully extended to other 2D systems such as As_2S_3 , GeS, MoO_3 , and CrSBr. Polarization-resolved optical microscopy reveals strong linear dichroism across centimeter-scale areas, confirming that the flakes are consistently aligned with minimal angular dispersion. We also performed STEM on selected flakes to verify the crystallographic orientation at the nanoscale. Importantly, electrical transport measurements confirm that the anisotropic optical response is accompanied by direction-dependent electrical conductivity, consistent with the intrinsic armchair–zigzag anisotropy of BP. Our approach combines the intrinsic flake quality typically associated with mechanical exfoliation with a scalable, parallelized deposition process. The ability to produce centimeter-scale anisotropic films with strongly preferential crystal orientation opens a practical route toward low-cost fabrication of devices that exploit in-plane anisotropy, such as polarization-sensitive photodetectors and directionally tuned

electronic components. This technique fills a gap between manual exfoliation and scalable deposition strategies, offering a route to fabricate large-area films with preferential flake orientation from low-symmetry van der Waals crystals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Crystals and substrates

CrSBr single crystals were prepared by a direct reaction of elemental chromium (99.99%, -60 mesh, Chemsavers, USA), bromine (99.9999%, Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic), and sulfur (99.9999%, Stanford Materials, USA) using a chemical vapor transport (CVT) synthesis recipe. 15 g of total material at the appropriate stoichiometric ratio was mixed in a quartz ampoule (35 × 220 mm) along with 4 at. % excess of bromine and sulfur. The material was pre-reacted at one end of the ampoule using a crucible furnace gradually heated to 700 °C over a period of 100 hours while the other end was kept below 200 °C. The heating procedure was repeated twice until the liquid bromine disappeared. The ampoule was then placed in a horizontal two-zone furnace for crystal growth. First, the growth zone was heated to 900 °C while the source zone was heated to 700 °C for 25 hours. For the growth step, the thermal gradient was reversed: the source zone was heated to 900 °C and the growth zone to 800 °C over a period of 12 days. Afterward, crystals with dimensions of up to 5 × 20 mm (with the long axis corresponding to the crystallographic a-axis) were removed from the ampoule in an argon glovebox.

MoO₃ were prepared by sublimation in air. 5g of MoO₃ (99.9%, -100 mesh, Strem, USA) were placed in quartz reactor inside quartz crucible and heated on 800°C (heating rate

5°C/min) for 50 hours with slow stream of air (50 ml/min) and freely cooled on room temperature. Sublimed crystals were cooled on the colder part of quartz reactor.

Black phosphorus was prepared by placing 80 mg of Sn, 40 mg SnI₄ and 2000 mg of red phosphorus (99.9999%, 1-6mm, Stanford Materials, USA) inside of a quartz ampoule (25x180 mm), followed by sealing of the ampoule using oxygen/hydrogen torch. Subsequently, the ampoule was heated at 400 °C for 1 hour using muffle furnace and leave in these conditions for 2 more hours. The temperature was then increased until 650 °C for 24 h. Finally, the muffle furnace was cooled down to 400 °C over 50 hours and over 25 hours on room temperature. The resulted plates (up to 5 mm x 2 mm) was washed with CS₂ to remove remains of white phosphorus formed during the synthesis and SnI₄. Germanium sulfide (GeS) crystals were grown by Prof. Der-Yuh Lin's group at the National Changhua University of Education (Taiwan).^[35] Arsenic trisulfide (As₂S₃) was obtained through mechanical exfoliation of highly crystalline natural orpiment mineral.^[36]

Polycarbonate substrates (thickness \approx 250 μ m) were purchased at Modulor GmbH. Device fabrication employed highly p-doped Si wafers with a 290 nm thermal SiO₂ layer with a resistivity of 0.001-0.005 Ohm/Cm (SiO₂/Si, Inseto).

Roll-to-roll exfoliation, film transfer and sample storage

We used a custom-designed mechanical exfoliation setup based on a roll-to-roll geometry, consisting of two cylinders with diameters in a 53:23 ratio. This ratio between prime numbers was chosen to minimize commensurability, ensuring that the same surface regions on the opposing rolls come into contact only after 1,219 full rotations. This quasi-incommensurate configuration prevents repeated exfoliation or accumulation at specific

locations on the tape, promoting more uniform material transfer across large areas. Both cylinders were covered with Nitto SPV 224 tape, and the bulk van der Waals material was placed on the tape of the source cylinder. Single crystals with well-defined in-plane anisotropy were carefully mounted with their orientation aligned relative to the rolling direction, ensuring that the exfoliated flakes maintain a consistent crystallographic alignment. The cylinders roll for 45 seconds at 500 rpm with an applied force between 20 N and 40 N in a fixed direction, the tape carrying the exfoliated flakes was pressed onto the target substrate, heated to 100 °C for 5 minutes to soften the adhesive, and then slowly peeled off, leaving a continuous aligned film on the substrate. In our current setup, the roll-to-roll exfoliation process achieves a throughput of approximately 2 cm²/min. This includes the time used for mounting the source crystal, the exfoliation process and the thermal release transfer of the film onto the target surface.

Since the roll-to-roll exfoliation method relies on the same adhesive material (Nitto SPV 224) and mechanical cleavage mechanism as conventional manual exfoliation, and operates under similarly mild conditions (room temperature rolling, moderate pressure, and low-speed contact), we do not expect it to introduce additional structural defects in the flakes beyond those typically present in mechanically exfoliated samples. This is supported by the high crystallinity observed in representative atomic-resolution STEM images (Figure 2d and Figure S4), and by the consistency of the optical and electrical anisotropy measurements with values reported for pristine BP flakes.

Moreover, the thermal release transfer does not appear to introduce significant surface contamination, as confirmed by XPS analysis in recent studies using identical tape and thermal protocols.^[37] All optical and electrical characterizations were carried out in ambient conditions shortly after fabrication, within timeframes where no measurable degradation was observed. For TEM analysis, samples were kept in dark conditions in

vacuum storage bags^[38] and remained stable for over 24 hours in typical Madrid humidity (20–30% RH).

Electronic and optical measurements

Current-voltage (I-V) measurements were carried out at room temperature using a home-built probe station equipped with a Keithley 2450 source-measure unit. Polarization-resolved optical microscopy was performed in transmission mode using a Motic BA310 MET microscope. A piezoelectrically actuated Thorlabs ELL14 rotation mount holding a linear polarizer was positioned between the halogen lamp and the condenser lenses. Images were acquired with an AMScope MU1803 digital camera. Polarization dependent photodetector measurements were acquired with a Keithley 2450 source-measure unit in a home-built probe station upon illumination with a home-built light source.^[39]

Device fabrication

(Anisotropic conductivity) Symmetrically arranged gold electrodes converging toward a central contact region were patterned on SiO₂ (290 nm)/p⁺⁺-Si substrates using maskless photolithography (SmartForce SmartPrint). After development, a 5 nm Cr adhesion layer followed by 45 nm of Au was deposited by thermal evaporation. Afterwards we do the lift-off process to remove the resist and obtain smooth and detail gold electrodes. Further fabrication details are provided in the Supporting Information. To enhance connectivity across the film, three successive BP transfers were performed, with careful alignment of the tape angle in both steps to preserve the global crystallographic orientation.

(CrSBr photodetector): Polarization-sensitive photodetectors were fabricated on flexible polycarbonate substrates using roll-to-roll exfoliated CrSBr films. To enhance connectivity across the film, two successive CrSBr transfers were performed, with careful alignment of the tape angle in both steps to preserve the global crystallographic

orientation. The metal electrodes (5 nm Cr / 50 nm Au) were deposited by thermal evaporation through a shadow mask (by Ossila). See Supporting Information for more details.

Atomic force microscopy

Topography was measured with a Nanotec AFM in dynamic mode under ambient conditions, using PPP-FMR silicon cantilevers (Nanosensors) with a nominal force constant and resonance frequency of 3 N m^{-1} and 75 kHz, respectively. Images were analysed with an open source program for scanning probe microscopy called Gwyddion.^[40]

(Scanning) transmission electron microscopy

BP flakes were transferred to Si_3N_4 membrane grids for TEM and STEM observation. TEM characterization was carried out using a JEM-F200 (JEOL Ltd.) installed at the University of Tokyo, operated at 200kV. STEM characterization was carried out using a JEOL JEM-ARM 200cF aberration-corrected electron microscope installed at the ICTS CNME-UCM and equipped with a cold field emission gun and a Gatan Metro In-Situ Counting Camera, operated at 200 kV. For 4D-STEM nano beam electron diffraction experiments, a convergence semi-angle of 2.7 mrad was used to separate the diffracted discs employed to measure the crystal orientation. For 4D-STEM acquisition, the electron beam was scanned across the region of interest and a NBED pattern was acquired for every pixel with a dwell time of 50 ms/pixel. The 4D-STEM dataset analyzed consists of 150×150 pixels for a total of 22,500 diffraction patterns. Crystal orientation was extracted by measuring the angle (θ) between the horizontal axis and the reciprocal lattice vector (\vec{g}) corresponding to the short lattice vector of the crystal of each diffraction pattern..

Author Contributions

A.C.G. conceived the project, designed the experiments and supervised the project. E.Z.A. and A.C.G. fabricated the anisotropic films and developed the characterization protocols. Y.S. and T.P. assisted with the preparation of the films and lithography. E.Z.A. and C.M. performed the AFM measurements. F.F.C., G.S.S., B.W., R.I., and M.V. performed the TEM measurements. JQB and PLA-R performed the polarization sensitive photodetector measurements. D.-Y.L. B.W. and Z.S. prepared the bulk anisotropic crystals. E.Z.A. and A.C.G. designed the figures and analyzed the data. A.C.G. drafted the manuscript with support from E.Z.A., and all authors reviewed and edited the final version.

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